

PARTHENOS

Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools
for Heritage E-research Networking,
Optimization and Synergies

First Year Communication Report, and Updated Communication Plan

KNAW-NIOD, PIN, FHP

19 July 2016

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the work of PARTHENOS WP8 “Communication, dissemination and outreach” during the first year of the project (May 2015-April 2016). It is an updated version of the PARTHENOS Deliverable D8.1 *Initial Communication Plan* that was produced in July 2015. Whereas the *Initial Communication Plan* presented an overall dissemination and communication strategy, and provided a detailed plan of relevant activities for the project’s first year, the present document reports on the implementation of this strategy, proposes minor corrections, and set out our plans for year 2. Throughout the project, we will continue to co-ordinate and evaluate the implementation of our communication and dissemination strategy and update reports will be prepared in months 27, 39 and 48 of the project.

The general objectives of PARTHENOS WP8 are to:

- disseminate effectively the project goals and outcomes;
- set up efficient tools for the communication towards various stakeholders (scientific communities, professionals, decisions makers, public, etc.);
- exploit synergies in liaisons and collaborations.

The present document demonstrates that we have succeeded in establishing a robust communication and dissemination infrastructure over the last twelve months, and thereby have laid the foundations for achieving our objectives. In particular, the document presents an overall assessment of the success of our existing communication and dissemination strategy, including necessary revisions (section 3); reports in detail on all relevant dissemination and communication tasks in the first year (section 4); provides a quantitative assessment of our activities against the evaluation criteria set in the *Initial Communication Plan* (section 5); and finally outlines our detailed plans for the next 12 months (section 6) and establishes revised evaluation criteria for this period (section 7).

2. Introduction

The PARTHENOS project is premised upon a collaboration of sixteen partners from nine European countries, comprising the two European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) active in the broad fields of the humanities – DARIAH and CLARIN – as well as institutions active in European research infrastructure projects – ARIADNE, CENDARI, CHARISMA/IPERION-CH, EHRI, DCH-RP. Marshalling such a comprehensive consortium, the PARTHENOS projects aims to:

- increase the cohesion of research sectors in the field of Language Studies, Digital Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Archaeology and related fields;
- define and implement common guidelines and best practices enabling cross-discipline data curation policies;
- establish a vision about shared virtual research methods for humanities supported by foresight studies;
- mainstream standardization and interoperability in order to support data sharing and re-use;
- develop common tools for data oriented services.

All these high-level aims are critically dependent upon successful collaboration between disparate infrastructures to increase their cohesion, inter-disciplinarily and inter-operability. Therefore, a coordinated and comprehensive approach to dissemination and communication is crucial for the project to achieve its aims and to maximise its impact.

Work package (WP) 8 is charged with planning, coordinating and implementing all of the project's communication and dissemination activities. In month three of the project, it delivered a comprehensive *Initial Communication Plan*¹ that:

- set out PARTHENOS' overall communication and dissemination strategy;
- identified the project's stakeholder communities;

¹ See Reto Speck et al. "D8.2 Initial Communication Plan", *PARTHENOS Deliverable*, July 2015, available at http://www.parthenos-project.eu/Download/Deliverables/D8.2_Initial_Communication_Plan.

- presented a set of core communication messages;
- analysed the communication resources available to the project;
- described the project's own communication channels and dissemination materials that are to be produced by the project;
- listed external dissemination opportunities;
- and set evaluation targets for the first 12 months.

The present document reports on the implementation of this plan during the first twelve months of the project (May 2015-April 2016) and contains the planning of communication and dissemination activities for the second year (May 2016-April 2017). It presents an overall assessment of the success of our existing communication and dissemination strategy, including necessary revisions (section 3); reports in detail on all relevant dissemination and communication tasks in the first year (section 4); provides a quantitative assessment of our activities against the evaluation criteria set in the initial plan (section 5); and finally outlines our detailed plans for the next 12 months (section 6) and establishes revised evaluation criteria for this period (section 7).

3. Revisions to communication and dissemination strategy

The overall communication and dissemination strategy outlined in sections 3-6 of the *Initial Communication Plan* has served the project well in its first year of operation. As will be shown in more detail in section 5 below, following this strategy has enabled us to reach, and even exceed, most of the targets set for the first twelve months.

In this section we will recapitulate in brief the main elements of our overall strategy - objectives, high-level communication and dissemination principles, stakeholder groups and tailored messages – and indicate, where relevant, necessary adjustments and revisions to the initial strategy.

3.1. Overall objectives

The PARTHENOS Description of Action defines three overall objectives for the project's communication and dissemination activities:

1. to disseminate effectively the project goals and outcomes;
2. to set up efficient tools for the communication towards various stakeholders (scientific communities, professionals, decisions makers, public, etc.)
3. to exploit synergies in liaisons and collaborations.

In order to achieve these general objectives, the *Initial Communication Plan* defines five specific objectives:

1. to identify and involve internal stakeholders within the partner organisations;
2. to create an affiliate network of external stakeholders (research infrastructures and networks in related fields);
3. to ensure that PARTHENOS reaches the core scientific communities in linguistic studies, digital humanities, digital heritage, archaeology and history, as well as professionals in related fields;

4. to raise awareness about PARTHENOS amongst policy makers, funding bodies and major related public institutions;
5. to devise a strategy to involve the general public and attract non-professional audiences.

We believe that both the general and specific objectives remain valid for our work, and that no major revisions are required. The only minor adjustment that is necessary is to change the reference to “linguistic studies” in the third specific objective to “language studies” (see also section 3.4 below for more details).

Furthermore, and as will become clear throughout this deliverable, we have made good progress towards achieving the objectives we have set for ourselves. In particular, we have successfully established the foundations over the past year upon which our future work can build. For instance, we have managed to establish solid communication tools that enable us to reach our various stakeholders; utilising this communication infrastructure will enable us to disseminate effectively the major project’s outcomes as they become available over the next three years. By the same token, we have succeeded in reaching out to our internal stakeholders, thereby creating an effective PARTHENOS communication network; the main goal for the remainder of the project is now to marshal this network to successively strengthen our ties to all our external stakeholders – researchers, policy makers and the general public – thereby ensuring the dissemination and impact of substantive project’s results.

3.2. Communication and dissemination principles

The *Initial Communication Plan* specifies five core communication and dissemination principles that should inform our activities:

1. **Adaptability.** Given the scope of the project and the specific themes involved, the communication strategy needs to be comprehensive enough to cover the project as a whole, while being adaptable to the project’s various research themes and stakeholder communities. For example, specific channels are to be used to reach particular target groups, and dissemination materials may have to be tailored to the needs of different end users.

2. **Flexibility.** As per the previous pillar, PARTHENOS' communication needs to be flexible and open, in order to create a responsive framework to changing needs and challenges.
3. **Dynamism.** The dynamic element is the natural consequence of the two points above. A dynamic strategy is a key to maximise the impact of PARTHENOS.
4. **Tailoring of messages/usage of appropriate language.** As stated above, PARTHENOS needs to be able to speak to academic audiences in a variety of fields, as well as to decision makers and the public at large. To achieve this, PARTHENOS will follow a multi-layered communication strategy that formulates core messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences, and expressed in appropriate language (specialised, technical communication vs. plain, jargon-free communication).
5. **Exploitation of synergies:** PARTHENOS is a clustering project across existing Research Infrastructures, integrating initiatives and e-infrastructures in the fields of Digital Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Language Studies², Archaeology and related fields. As such, the project can draw upon a plethora of expertise, networks and dissemination and communication channels that are already in existence at partner institutions and related projects and that can reach the specific subject communities with which PARTHENOS wishes to engage. PARTHENOS needs to exploit to the fullest the synergy that can be achieved by building bridges between these existing resources, and must avoid a duplication of effort. Therefore, achieving better co-ordination and cross-fertilisation of existing communication and dissemination activities is central to PARTHENOS' mission.

As with the objectives, these principles have proven their use and do not need a major update for the project's second year. On the contrary, we should strive to implement these principles even more forcefully over the next period. This is particularly true in regard to the exploitation of synergies principle. Whereas it was crucial during the first twelve months to establish solid communication foundations, which required decisive and centrally co-ordination action of a small core communication and dissemination team, we are now in a position where we should endeavour to fully exploit the communication networks, expertise and channels that are in existence across all PARTHENOS partner institutions and affiliated projects.

² In the *Initial Communication Plan* we referred to "Linguistic Studies" rather than "Language Studies". We have since adopted the terminology for the reasons explained in section 3.4 below.

3.3. Stakeholder groups

The *Initial Communication Plan* identifies and analyses a set of stakeholder communities, and classifies these into three groups according to the influence and mutual dependence that exist between these communities and PARTHENOS. **Error! Reference source not found.** below provides a visual representation of our initial stakeholder analysis:

¹ Research Infrastructures

² Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums

Figure 1: Stakeholder map

During the project's first year, we have not identified any additional stakeholder communities which merit inclusion in our stakeholder map, nor have we detected any major problems with our detailed stakeholder analysis.

In terms of engaging stakeholder communities, the focus during the first period was in the first instance on “direct” stakeholders – partners and affiliated Research Infrastructures – but we have already started the process of also reaching out to “close” and “societal” ones. The priority for the forthcoming period is to maintain and strengthen our existing relationship with direct stakeholders and to successively reach out more vigorously to “close” and, towards the end of the second period, “societal” stakeholder communities.

3.4. Tailored messages

The *Initial Communication Plan* defines five messages tailored towards the achievement of particular communication goals and towards particular stakeholder groups. These messages are:

- General message
- Extended general message
- Research and educational message
- Jargon-free public message
- Policy- and decision-maker message

These messages have successfully informed our communication and dissemination activities during the first period, particularly the “general message” and the “research and educational message”. The only revision required at this point relates to the enumeration of the various disciplinary subject communities that PARTHENOS seeks to address. In the current General message and Extended general message, this enumeration reads as follows:

PARTHENOS aims at strengthening the cohesion of research in the broad sector of *Linguistic Studies, Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Archaeology*

and related fields through a thematic cluster of European Research Infrastructures, integrating initiatives and infrastructures, and building bridges between different, although tightly, interrelated fields.

Within WP8 a number of concerns were voiced in regard to this enumeration: first, “Linguistics Studies” does not encompass all the language related disciplines that PARTHENOS seeks to address via CLARIN; secondly, there is no reference to “Digital Humanities”, an important field for, for instance, DARIAH; finally, treating the “Humanities” at large in the same way as, say, “History” or “Archaeology” is inconsistent. In consultation with the PARTHENOS Steering Committee we have tried to overcome these difficulties, and have settled on an alternative enumeration as follows:

PARTHENOS AIMS AT STRENGTHENING THE COHESION OF RESEARCH IN THE BROAD SECTOR OF HISTORY, LANGUAGE STUDIES, CULTURAL HERITAGE, ARCHAEOLOGY, AND RELATED FIELDS ACROSS THE (DIGITAL) HUMANITIES.

4. Report on activities during first year

This section provides short narrative reports on the major activities undertaken in WP8 for the period May 2015 to April 2016. A summary assessment of these activities against the targets set in the *Initial Communication Plan* is provided in section 5.

4.1. Website

The project website – available via <http://www.parthenos-project.eu> – is one of our main dissemination channels. It is a hub for all the information about the project and its activities, events and services, and constitutes an important source of information for our stakeholder communities. Apart from directly hosting a wealth of content, it also contains links to relevant information available elsewhere such as publications, presentations, etc. As such it offers stakeholder one-stop access to information about the project's background, ambition and results.

The project website was officially launched in June 2015. It has since been continuously updated with new content, and its layout and logical structure was revised in January 2016. Section 4.1.1 an overview of the content that we have produced during the first year as well as an outline of the site's structure, whereas section 4.1.2 analyses the usage of the site across the first year.

4.1.1. Content and structure

During the first twelve months of PARTHENOS, we published fifty three news items on the website, and further promoted these items via Twitter and our mailing list.

We believe that the content production rate is more than satisfactory. Indeed, on average we have been able to issue one article per week during the first twelve months, thus keeping the website up-to-date and attractive and informative for both first and returning visitors.

We initially categorised all news items according to nine distinct classes. However, it became apparent that this categorisation was too granular, and we therefore decided to restructure the site and overhaul its layout in January 2016.

This overhaul aimed at delivering a better user experience, by simplifying navigation of the site and by providing visitors with at-a-glance access to all the relevant information (see Figure 2).

To facilitate this we reduced the number of categories by which content is classified to three:

- *News*, which includes all PARTHENOS' related news, features and updates;
- *Partners' news*, which includes news and updates coming from the consortium's partners that are considered to be relevant for the communities the project serves;
- *Announcements*, which includes updates and interesting opportunities for the communities PARTHENOS serves, such as conferences, workshops, call for papers etc.

This new content organisation was applied retroactively to all the content already published before January 2016. It is important to note that several categories may apply for the same content, for example in the case of a call for paper published by a partner.

By way of overview, the fifty three unique news items published in year one are divided as follows:

- 31 items in the category *News*
 - 6 news items were labeled as feature, long form news
- 16 items in the category *Partners' news*
- 10 items in the category *Announcements*

Overall, we deem this to be a good split between the different categories with the major of items relating directly to PARTHENOS, while still giving ample space to other news that may be of interest to the PARTHENOS community.

As mentioned, the updated content organization was also reflected in an user experience overhaul realised in M09 following WP8 internal recommendations.

Figure 2 below shows the current PARTHENOS' homepage, structured vertically into three different blocks (highlighted) that are separated visually and contextually. The homepage thus clearly highlights news related directly to PARTHENOS', but still offers a prominent place to news items and the announcements sourced from the consortium's partners.

Figure 2: PARTHENOS homepage layout

4.1.2. Analytics

We have carefully monitored usage of the website via Google Analytics since its launch in June 2016. We produced a mid-term internal analytics report entitled “Website Usage Analysis M01 – M06” in November 2015 that contained recommendations to build upon the positive results of the first six months. The analysis below covers the whole first year period, and confirms that we are on track in regard to website traffic.

Overall, the PARTHENOS website attracted 4,526 users in the first 12 months of project's lifetime. The official release date of the site in June 2015, combined with the expected surge in visitor numbers created by the project's Kick-Off meeting in July 2015, is clearly visible in Figure 3. After a natural decrease throughout the month of August 2015, the general trend of the website – both in terms of users and sessions – is positive.

Figure 3: Website analytics - general overview

In terms of page views, the main catalyst of traffic is the website’s home page. In terms of content, the ten most visited pages are about the project’s description (/consortium, /about-the-project, /the-approach, /news, /activities-and-wps/). It should also be noted that the page /about-the-project/faq managed to enter the top-10 despite having only been published in March 2016.

In general, the average session duration and the average pages per session ratio prove that the contents published to date were able to provide a **good level of users’ retention**. The engagement funnel is shown in Figure 4. As expected, the biggest users’ drop-off occurs at the very beginning of the browsing experience. In total, 1/3 of all sessions were converted into further actions (clicks).

Figure 4: Website analytics - users' funnel

Access to the website is highly dependent on direct access rather than organic search, referral or direct marketing acquisition (such newsletters and social networks), see Figure 5. However, we implemented significant improvements in terms of SEO and referral in response to the “Website Usage Analysis M01 – M06” report issued in November 2015, which may help to re-balance traffic acquisition in the future.

It is also interesting to note that most of the people who landed on our website through search engines such as Google (33%) are also the ones who were more likely to spend more time (2:35 minutes) on the website, browsing an average of three pages per session. Similarly, the users acquired via email marketing show a high degree of engagement.

Default Channel Grouping	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Sessions ? ↓	% New Sessions ?	New Users ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
NOReferral	6,983 % of Total: 76.30% (9,152)	64.86% Avg for View: 71.61% (-9.43%)	4,529 % of Total: 69.10% (6,554)	62.47% Avg for View: 68.48% (-8.78%)	2.28 Avg for View: 1.99 (14.58%)	00:02:02 Avg for View: 00:01:40 (22.85%)
1. Direct	2,518 (36.06%)	75.18%	1,893 (41.80%)	72.99%	2.00	00:01:38
2. Organic Search	2,317 (33.18%)	62.58%	1,450 (32.02%)	49.59%	2.79	00:02:35
3. Referral	1,241 (17.77%)	73.17%	908 (20.05%)	66.00%	2.02	00:01:27
4. Social	864 (12.37%)	31.48%	272 (6.01%)	62.38%	2.09	00:02:24
5. Email	43 (0.62%)	13.95%	6 (0.13%)	39.53%	3.23	00:06:27

Figure 5: Website analytics - acquisition

As shown in Figure 6, the referral traffic³ comes mostly from project partners' websites and from the newsletter (**.campaign-archive2.com domains).

<input type="checkbox"/>	Source [?]	Acquisition		
		Sessions [?] ↓	% New Sessions [?]	New Users [?]
	NOReferral	2,105 % of Total: 26.55% (7,929)	56.06% Avg for View: 67.32% (-16.73%)	1,180 % of Total: 22.11% (5,338)
<input type="checkbox"/>	1. t.co	748 (35.53%)	27.81%	208 (17.63%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	2. us11.campaign-archive2.com	99 (4.70%)	12.12%	12 (1.02%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	3. humanum.hypotheses.org	98 (4.66%)	82.65%	81 (6.86%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	4. adf.ly	74 (3.52%)	100.00%	74 (6.27%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	5. huma-num.fr	60 (2.85%)	61.67%	37 (3.14%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	6. facebook.com	45 (2.14%)	55.56%	25 (2.12%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	7. kcl.ac.uk	38 (1.81%)	68.42%	26 (2.20%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	8. oeaw.ac.at	38 (1.81%)	60.53%	23 (1.95%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	9. snip.to	38 (1.81%)	100.00%	38 (3.22%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	10. images.google.fr	35 (1.66%)	88.57%	31 (2.63%)

Figure 6: Website analytics - site referrals

The social referrals are coming mostly from Twitter (Figure 7), which also granted a good level of engagement (high average session duration and page/sessions) for users brought to our website via this platform.

³ Getting meaningful analytics from referral traffic is difficult given the enormous amount of so-called referral spam that targets any website, including parthenos-project.eu. The referral spam does not generate any actual visits, but it leave traces when it comes to identifying and analysing the main sources of referral. In order to overcome this major annoyance and to get the most meaningful and actionable analytics we have developed a regex expression within Google Analytics that automatically filters out referral spam. The regex is updated and assessed on a weekly basis, in order to prevent malicious data entering the analytics' reports.

Figure 7: Website analytics - social network referrals

4.2. Social media

PARTHENOS takes full advantage of the most used and effective social networks to support its dissemination activities. We thereby take full advantage of the extensive social networks that are already in existence within the consortium.

4.2.1. Twitter

Twitter is central to our social media strategy. A PARTHENOS twitter account (@PARTHENOS_EU) was setup in month one of the project, and has been widely used to report on the project's activities, and alert followers to new content on the website.

Over the last twelve month we have produced 134 distinct tweets that have been read by a steadily increasing group of followers. By 30 April 2016, @PARTHENOS_Eu was followed by 208 twitter users, and, over the period May 2015 to April 2016, our tweets have achieved an average monthly number of tweet impressions of 5,702. Figure 8 demonstrates that we have been able to steadily increase the number of impressions our

tweets generate over the last year, while Figure 9 demonstrates the steady increase in the number of our followers over the same period.

Figure 8: Tweets and tweet impressions

Figure 9: New twitter followers

Table 1, finally, reports on the ten most effective tweets we have issued in 2016.

Text	Date	Impressi	Interacti	Interaction rate
In our Partner in Parthenos web features: focus on coordinator PIN ScrI. in Florence. Read more, https://t.co/mq66NjgNFG	2016-04-28 13:25	+0000 281.0	5.0	0.01779359 430604982 4
Call for Applications for @Ariadne_Network summer schools and individual training in 2016! https://t.co/4Zd7GTKThC #archaeology #cfa2016	2016-04-18 10:22	+0000 140.0	2.0	0.01428571 428571428 5
@Ariadne_Network posted interesting #opportunities for scholars and researchers https://t.co/4Zd7GTKThC	2016-04-15 08:42	+0000 65.0	1.0	0.01538461 538461538 5
Good morning! @CLARINERIC is searching for Director for User Involvement. More info here https://t.co/CkTSdB6fO6 #jobopportunity	2016-04-14 07:43	+0000 638.0	7.0	0.01097178 68338558
@DANSKNAW is looking for Information scientist/Data science engineer #jobopportunity #PARTHENOS . More info here https://t.co/Hu1ZRnvyRq	2016-04-11 14:58	+0000 68.0	3.0	0.04411764 705882353
Save the date! @Eudat_eu Webinar on Trust and Certification planned for Monday, 18th April https://t.co/6itL7OClz4	2016-04-08 08:29	+0000 334.0	5.0	0.01497005 988023952 1
Today, the 3rd community workshop on the European Open Science, organized with among others PARTHENOS, follow #EOSC, https://t.co/zdFuGngnWe	2016-04-07 08:34	+0000 227.0	1.0	0.00440528 634361233 5
"Just what do digital humanists really do?, À Find out and participate @DayofDH next Friday, April 8, https://t.co/sTOCVfauu3	2016-04-04 10:47	+0000 1002.0	28.0	0.02794411 177644710 5
On 7 April, PARTHENOS, À coordinator Franco Niccolucci takes part in the 3rd community workshop on EOSC @EGI_eu conf, https://t.co/pqa7HP6I2l	2016-03-31 14:23	+0000 238.0	7.0	0.02941176 470588235 3

Table 1: Top ten tweets

Table 1 indicates that the *most suitable time to tweet PARTHENOS' related news appears to be the in the morning*. This confirms a trend we have already identified in a previous assessment of our Twitter activities. We of course should not draw strong conclusions from a very small sample of tweets, but it is nonetheless important to keep track of the trend to see if the assumption is confirmed.

4.2.2. Other social media channels

A Youtube channel has also been setup (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnKJnFo_IFoAl3VH51t1hw). At present, the channel features two videos from the beginning of the project, and a recording of the webinar 'How to write use cases' that was held in October 2015. With 47 views this video reached a small, but focused audience. We will continue to use YouTube to host short videos that document forthcoming PARTHENOS meetings and events, as well as all other audio-visual outputs produced by the various PARTHENOS WPs.

At the start of the project a Flickr account was created to share the project’s photographic documentation. The official PARTHENOS page is available at <https://www.flickr.com/people/136244307@N08/>. Since then it has been used to host the photo streams of major events such as the Kick-off meeting.

Slideshare has proven its value as a successful media channel to other, similar projects, and therefore PARTHENOS has opened its own account, <http://www.slideshare.net/Parthenos>. It already features the PARTHENOS general PowerPoint and will be used to disseminate the growing number of presentations as the project evolves.

4.3. Mailing list

Website visitors can sign-up to a PARTHENOS’ email-list, hosted on the Mailchimp platform. Currently, this email list is chiefly used for sending out our period newsletters (see section 4.4 below), but it can of course also be used for other dissemination purposes.

During the first twelve month we have successfully populated the list, and as of 30 April 2016, we had 162 subscribers. 104 people were bulk subscribed from existing contact lists in July 2015, but as Figure 10 below shows, we have since been able to steadily increase the number of subscribers.

Figure 10: Growth PARTHENOS mailing list

4.4. Newsletters

PARTHENOS periodically sends out newsletters to all subscribers on our email list. The newsletter provides readers with a concise summary of all the latest PARTHENOS-related news, as well as updates about important developments in the various fields related to PARTHENOS' activities.

During the first year, we have produced four Newsletters: July 2015, October 2015, December 2015, March 2016.

4.5. Press relations

In the first twelve months, PARTHENOS issued a total of eight press releases, seven focusing on the project's launch and its aftermaths and one focusing on one of the project's activities – the gathering of user requirements.

Many specialised blogs and several Italian newspapers in their online editions published the seven press releases issued before and after the Kick-Off meeting in July 2015. One of these press releases was jointly issued together with the projects IPERION-CH and E-RIHS that were also launched in Florence at the same time of PARTHENOS.

In July 2015, WP8 worked together with WP2 to issue a press release to present the start of WP2 activities and the expected results. This press release, which was also rendered as a news item in parthenos-project.eu, was also aimed at testing the effectiveness of PARTHENOS' press releases focused more on project's processes than on its final outcomes, and to track the reactions of online and offline news agency towards the project's activities.

It should be noted that, contrary to what happened during the kick-off in July 2015, this activity-related press release did not result in major interest from news providers.

The main reason is that media tend to focus on concrete, actionable outputs rather than on processes when defining their news' agenda. Therefore, WP8 has decided to go for a smart approach toward the issuing of press releases, and release them only when actionable and news-worthy content is available for the press.

The next foreseen press release will likely coincide with the launch of the 2016 PARTHENOS' flagship communication initiative, as described in section 6.1.

4.6. Publicity materials

To help all partners with their PARTHENOS-related dissemination activities, WP8 is charged with the creation of appropriate publicity materials. The *Initial Communication Plan* contains details about the logo, visual style guidelines and a set of templates that were made available to partners at the beginning of the project. In addition, we have developed the following materials over the course of the first year:

- A general PowerPoint presentation
- A poster
- A flyer

4.6.1. General PowerPoint presentation

The aim of the general PowerPoint presentation is to give a high-level overview of the PARTHENOS project. Partners using it are encouraged to adapt it in such a way that it fulfils their particular communication goals. Over the past year, this general presentation was used on at least three occasions:

- Sara di Giorgio at EGI Community Forum 2015, Showcasing tools and services from Research Infrastructures, Rome, 10-13 November 2015.
- Hella Hollander at the National Symposium for Dutch Archaeologists (Reuwendagen), 26 November 2015.
- Franco Niccolucci at the JPI on Cultural Heritage meeting in Brussels, 12 February 2016.

4.6.2. Poster

The PARTHENOS poster provides an at-a-glance overview of the project. It was especially created for the Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum (DHd) conference in Leipzig, March 7-12, 2016, where it was shown at the DARIAH-DE and CLARIN-D booths. An earlier version was created by Vanessa Hanneschläger (among others) and shown at the Digital Humanities Austria conference in Vienna, 30 November – 2 December, 2015.

PARTHENOS Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies

Who is PARTHENOS?
PARTHENOS is a consortium of 16 partners that are committed to performing the tasks described in the project's work programme. But PARTHENOS also relies on the support of many other individuals and organisations in the broad fields of (digital) humanities.

Why PARTHENOS?
The PARTHENOS project empowers digital research in the fields of History, Language Studies, Cultural Heritage, Archaeology, and related fields across the (Digital) Humanities. PARTHENOS brings together several existing research infrastructures to make it easier to find and combine information from different domains. PARTHENOS joins together data and people from many humanities disciplines, and by working collaboratively will:

- Develop common standards to ease exploitation
- Coordinate joint activities among research projects
- Harmonize policy definition and implementation
- Pool methods and services
- Share solutions to the same problems
- Bring people and their expertise together

What results will PARTHENOS produce?
PARTHENOS will establish the foundations for future interoperability of the humanities by producing:

- a coherent, authoritative, well accepted set of policies, guidelines and tools concerning the management of data lifecycle and related issues such as IPR;
- a wide set of standards and semantics, originated from community needs and tailored to the methodology and intended use by researchers;
- a coherent set of tools for carrying out research using and re-using data.

How to get involved?
PARTHENOS continually expands the group of institutions and people associated with the project. Interested parties can follow the project's development and progress:

www.parthenos-project.eu
Twitter @Parthenos_EU

Subscribe to the PARTHENOS' newsletter, www.parthenos-project.eu/category/news

PARTHENOS is funded by Horizon2020 of the European Commission. The project started on 1 May 2015 and runs for 48 months.

Figure 11: PARTHENOS poster

4.6.3. Flyer

The Parthenos flyer was designed in October 2015, and partners were encouraged to order copies for distribution at relevant events.

5,000 copies were ordered and approximately 4,030 were distributed to the partners.

Organisation	Person	Nr. of copies
CLARIN – Institute of Computer Science, Polish Academy of Sciences	Maciej Ogrodniczuk	200
University of Applied Sciences Potsdam	Jenny Oltersdorf	500
CENDARI / TCD	Jennifer Edmond	100
Meertens Institute (KNAW)	Douwe Zeldenrust	30
KCL	Mark Hedges	200

TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS)	Adeline Joffres	500
Academy of Athens	Eleni Vernardaki	150
FORTH	Kostas Stefanidis	100
DANS (KNAW)	Hella Hollander	50
CNR	Anna Molino	1,000
CSIC	Marta Castillejo	100
NIOD (KNAW)	Conny Kristel	100
CLARIN - University of Leipzig	Stefanie Löpke	500
CLARIN ERIC	Sebastian Drude	400
IESL-FORTH	Panayiotis Siozos	100
PIN	Stefano Sbarbati	300
Total		4,030

Table 2: Distribution of flyer to partners

Several flyers were ordered for and distributed at specific events:

Event	Date	Person/organisation
National Symposium for Dutch Archaeologists (Reuwendagen)	26 November 2015, Zwolle	Hella Hollander, DANS
DHd 2016	March 2016, Leipzig	Stefanie Löpke, University of Leipzig (CLARIN)
TLT Conference and TextLink meeting (CLARIN)	December 2015, Poland	Maciej Ogródniczuk, Institute of Computer Science, Polish Academy of Sciences (CLARIN)
CENDARI Launch Event	14 January 2016, Berlin	Jennifer Edmond, CENDARI
LREC2016 (10th International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation)	May 23-28, 2016, Slovenia	Sebastian Drude
11th International Conference on Open	13-16 June, 2016, Dublin	Anders Sparre Conrad, CLARIN Denmark

Repositories 2016,

OR2016

European Summer
School in DH

Summer 2016, Leipzig

Stefanie Lapke, University
of Leipzig (CLARIN)

Table 3: Distribution of flyers at events

PARTHENOS
Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools
for Heritage E-research Networking,
Optimization and Synergies

Investing in culture is investing in the future

The PARTHENOS project empowers digital research in the fields of History, Language Studies, Cultural Heritage, Archaeology, and related fields across the (Digital) Humanities.

European Research Infrastructures
Digital technologies have led to the creation of large digital archives, and to a variety of innovative research methodologies applicable to these archives. We are now eager to integrate these archives and new methods to support digital research. This is the mission of new pan-European bodies, called European Research Infrastructures.

Research infrastructures enable the international scientific community to better conduct top-flight research by providing integrated facilities and resources. PARTHENOS supports the work of two research infrastructures, CLARIN (language resources) and DARIAH (digital humanities), as well as various integration projects addressing the cultural domain.

By working together, PARTHENOS will

- develop common standards to ease exploitation;
- coordinate joint activities among research projects;
- harmonize policy definition and implementation;
- pool methods and services;
- and share solutions to the same problems.

Would you like to know more?
Visit www.parthenos-project.eu

PARTHENOS stands for "Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies". It is inspired by the name of Athena Parthenos, the Greek goddess of wisdom, inspiration and civilization.

PARTHENOS is funded by Horizon2020 of the European Commission. The project started on 1 May 2015 and runs for 48 months.

Figure 12: PARTHENOS flyer front

PARTHENOS
Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools
for Heritage E-research Networking,
Optimization and Synergies

Culture shapes our identities, aspirations and relations to others and the world.

Individual researchers

Individual researchers will benefit from the advanced services made available to everybody by PARTHENOS, and can have a voice in the project development by communicating their needs and wishes. Such services concern all aspects of data management, including: access to and sharing of data; management of intellectual property rights; integration of diverse datasets; tools for discovering openly available resources; guidelines, training and education.

Would you like to know more? Please, visit www.parthenos-project.eu

Researchers may already take advantage of the great work and activities undertaken by Parthenos' sixteen partners:

- DARIAH-EU
- CLARIN ERIC
- PIN s.c.r.l. Italy (coordinator)
- KNAW, The Netherlands
- CNRS Huma-Num, France
- King's College London, UK
- University of Applied Sciences Potsdam, Germany
- Inria, France
- Trinity College Dublin, Ireland
- CSIC, Spain
- OEAW, Austria
- SISMEL, Italy
- CNR, Italy
- FORTH, Greece
- MIBACT-ICCU, Italy
- Academy of Athens, Greece

More information available at www.parthenos-project.eu/consortium

PARTHENOS also collaborates with other research infrastructure projects, such as ARIADNE (Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe), CENDARI (Collaborative European Digital Archive Infrastructure) and EHRI (European Holocaust Research Infrastructure).

Figure 13: PARTHENOS flyer back

4.7. Publications

As was expected, no peer-reviewed PARTHENOS-related publications were submitted during the first year of the project. However, the following non-peer reviewed items were published:

- Huma-Num website, Stéphane Pouyllau “Le programme PARTHENOS”, 28-04-2015, <http://humanum.hypotheses.org/1212>
- Website ÖAW-ACDH, “H2020 project approved!”, <http://www.oeaw.ac.at/acdh/en/H2020>
- Resolvo website, “H2020 Parthenos European Project”, 20 May 2015, <http://www.resolvo.eu/en/european-projects-h2020-parthenos-project/>
- NeMIS website (CNR), “PARTHENOS”, <http://nemis.isti.cnr.it/projects/parthenos>
- On LinkedIn, Kostas Stefanidis, “The PARTHENOS Project”, 11 June 2015, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/parthenos-project-kostas-stefanidis>
- Website CSIC, “CSIC partnership in two Horizon 2020 projects, IPERION CH and PARTHENOS”, http://www.igfr.csic.es/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=248:csic-partnership-in-two-horizon-2020-projects-iperion-ch-and-parthenos&catid=48:outreach-and-activities&Itemid=281&lang=en
- Website KCL, “Innovating research in the humanities and cultural heritage sectors – PARTHENOS begins its work”, 14 July 2015, <http://www.kcl.ac.uk/artshums/depts/ddh/newsrecords/2015/euhorizon2020grant-markhedges.aspx>
- NIOD website, “Vernieuwing in de internationale erfgoedsector - Start Parthenos project”, 16 July 2015, <http://www.niod.nl/nl/nieuws/vernieuwing-de-internationale-erfgoedsector-start-parthenos-project>
- ARIADNE website, “PARTHENOS Kicks off”, 21 July 2015, <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/PARTHENOS-Kicks-off>
- Website DIGHUMLAB Denmark, “Innovating The Heritage Research Sector – PARTHENOS Begins Its Work”, 24 July 2014, <http://dighumlab.com/blog/2015/07/24/innovating-the-heritage-research-sector-parthenos-begins-its-work/>

- EHRI website, “Innovating the Heritage Research Sector - PARTHENOS Begins Its Work”, 24-08-2015, <http://www.ehri-project.eu/innovating-heritage-research-sector-parthenos-begins-its-work>
- CLARIN website, “The PARTHENOS’ project in a nutshell”, <https://www.clarin.eu/content/factsheet-clarin-parthenos>
- Website Trinity Centre for Digital Humanities, “PARTHENOS meets in Dublin to Develop Training Plan for DH Infrastructures”, 20 February 2016, <http://dh.tcd.ie/dh/parthenos-meets-in-dublin-to-develop-training-plan-for-dh-infrastructures/>

4.8. Events

WP8 is responsible for coordinating an appropriate PARTHENOS presence at relevant external events, as well as for organising a series of joint events over the course of the project.

4.8.1. External events

The *Initial Communication Plan* contains a list of events that we intended to target at the outset of the project. In order to keep this list up-to-date and to aid co-ordination, we further setup two Basecamp calendars and populated these with details of such events. These calendars are:

- External events to target [\(https://basecamp.com/2932505/calendars/1476303/calendar_events\)](https://basecamp.com/2932505/calendars/1476303/calendar_events): identified relevant events with no confirmed PARTHENOS presence.
- External events with PARTHENOS presence [\(https://basecamp.com/2932505/calendars/1476304/calendar_events\)](https://basecamp.com/2932505/calendars/1476304/calendar_events): identified relevant events where PARTHENOS has a confirmed presence.

In addition, a google spreadsheet has been setup to keep track of PARTHENOS’ presence at past events (see <http://tinyurl.com/juoau93>) .

In the first year, PARTHENOS partners participated at the following events to disseminate information about the project:

Date	Event	Type of contribution	Organiser	Link
1-3 Sep 2015	NISE Annual Gathering, Swansea	Oral presentation	National Movements and Intermediary Structures in Europe (NISE)	http://nise.eu
24 Sep 2015	LINDAT/CLARIN Digital Humanities Workshop	Oral presentation	LINDAT/CLARIN	https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/events/seminar-o-digitalnich-zdrojich-sluzbach-ve-spolecenskych-humanitnich-vedach-wdh-2015
6 Oct 2015	2nd Spanish DH Conference: Asociación de Humanidades Digitales Hispánicas	Oral presentation	Asociación de Humanidades Digitales Hispánicas	http://hdh2015.linhd.es/
08-10 Nov 2015	#dariahTeach Open Humanities Workshop, Belgrade	Oral presentation	DARIAH Teach (Erasmus Plus Network)	http://dariah.eu/teach/index.php/2015/05/21/welcome-to-dariahteach/ http://dariah.rs/en/dariahteach-open-humanities-workshop/
10 Nov 2015	EGI Community Forum 2015, Rome	Oral presentation	EGI	http://cf2015.egi.eu/prgramme/
23-25 Nov 2015	Methodological Journeys of 3D Huma-Num's consortium	Oral presentation and distribution of information (flyers)	3D Huma-Num's consortium	https://shs3d.hypotheses.org/actualite/actualite-du-consortium-3d
26 Nov 2015	Reuvsdagen – main national symposium for Dutch Archaeologists	Oral presentation	Stichting Reuvs	www.reuvsdagen.nl
30 Nov	Digital Humanities Austria	Poster	Austrian Centre for	http://www.oeaw.ac.at

2015-02 Dec 2015	Conference	presentation	Digital Humanities (ACDH) of the Austrian Academy of Sciences	/acdh/en/dha2015-conf-report
11-12 Dec 2015	14th International Workshop on Treebanks and Linguistic Theories (TLT14)	Distribution of information	TLT workshop series	http://tlt14.ipipan.waw.pl/
17-19 Dec 2015	Convegno annuale AIUCD	Oral and poster presentation / distribution of info	Associazione per l'Informatica Umanistica e la Cultura Digitale	http://www.aiucd2015.unito.it/
14 Jan 2016	Cendari Launch	Distribution of flyers	Cendari project	http://www.cendari.eu/about/news/cendari-launch-great-success
1 Feb 2016	Interconsortia journey of Huma-Nums' consortia	Oral presentation	Huma-Num archipolis consortium	http://archipolis.hypotheses.org/423
12 Feb 2016	JPI CHI meeting, Brussels	Oral presentation	JPI on Cultural Heritage	http://www.jpi-culturalheritage.eu/
8 Mar 2016	2nd EADH Day at the DHd conference	Oral presentation	University of Leipzig/Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum	http://www.dhd2016.de/
09-11 Mar 2016	DHd conference	Distribution of info at booth (poster and flyers)	University of Leipzig/Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum	http://www.dhd2016.de/
7 Apr 2016	EGI Conference 2016. Opening Science in Europe and in the World: Third Community Workshop on Open Science Cloud	Oral presentation	EGI	https://indico.egi.eu/indico/event/2875/session/21/?slotId=0#20160407

Table 4: Event participation

Apart from co-ordinating contributions by individual partners to external events, WP8 also helped to co-organise a multi-partner venture: a five minute lightning talk entitled “Why

pool activities, resources and tools? Integrating and involving user communities in PARTHENOS“ which was presented by Vanessa Hanneschläger of OEAW on the 8th March at the second annual European Association for the Digital Humanities Symposium (EADH Day) held in conjunction with the 3rd International Conference of the Association Digital Humanities which took place at the University of Leipzig from the 7th to the 12th of March 2016. The main theme of the DHd conference was “Modellierung - Vernetzung - Visualisierung. Die Digital Humanities als fächerübergreifendes Forschungsparadigma” (Modelling - Networking - Visualisation. Digital Humanities as a transdisciplinary research paradigm). The paper was written collaboratively by PIN, KNAW-NIOD and OEAW. The presentation attracted much interest from the mainly German-speaking audience who asked several questions about PARTHENOS.

4.8.2. Joint events

Joint events are symposia, workshops, public presentations, etc. that are directly managed by PARTHENOS, the co-organisations of such events with other initiatives, and the participation with PARTHENOS-specific sessions, seminars, workshops etc. at events organised by third parties.

As the dissemination and discussion of substantive research results is the main aim of such events, it was clear from the outset that the majority of these events will happen in the latter part of the project.

A first attempt at organising a joint workshop was made for the Digital Humanities Conference on the 11th-16th July in Krakow (DH2016) which was judged to be an ideal audience. The theme of the paper “Users of DH Research Infrastructures: Who Are They, What Are Their Needs, And How To Get Them Involved?” written by CLARIN with support from DARIAH and CENDARI, was submitted in mid-February and was based on the experiences and issues raised from the research undertaken for WP2 in gathering the user requirements. The proposal included the delivery of a white paper on the topic (by the end of 2016). Unfortunately, the proposal had a mixed reception from the reviewers and was rejected as the overall score was not high enough. However, PARTHENOS will be represented by TCD on Monday 11th July at DH2016 as the workshop proposal “The Contribution of Research Infrastructures to DH Training” was successful.

4.9. Scientific communication

WP8 is tasked to analyse, support and improve scientific communication in the PARTHENOS target areas of language studies, digital humanities, digital heritage, archaeology and history. In particular, the WP8 Scientific Communication task aims to evaluate the creation of a scientific e-journal and the adoption and management of an Open Access repository for pre-print storage of scientific paper.

In the course of the first year we had hoped to undertake a comprehensive analysis and evaluation of existing relevant Open Access e-journals and repositories in order to establish detailed requirements for the future work of the Scientific Communication task.

Unfortunately, progress in this task has been uneven in the first year due to the following reasons:

- *Shift of partners:* The University of Göttingen (UGoe) was foreseen to lead the Scientific Communication task. Due to the project-wide transfer of responsibilities from UGoe to the Fachhochschule Potsdam (FHP), activities in this task started with a delay of four months.
- *Change of staff:* The person responsible leading the Scientific Communication task, and the closely related WP2 task Requirements of Scientific Communication, Dr Juliane Stiller, left the FHP and PARTHENOS in November 2015. There was a delay of almost four months before a replacement, Claus Spiecker, could be recruited.

While these delays are unfortunate, they are nevertheless manageable, not least as there are no major downward dependencies from the Scientific Communication task to other PARTHENOS activities. Moreover, we were able to minimise the effects of the delays by combining some activities of the Scientific Communication Task and the Requirements of Scientific Communication Task into a joint WP2/8 effort.

In order to investigate and evaluate the necessity and potential implementation of a new scientific e-journal and/or an open access repository, we started by collecting information on already existing e-journals and open access repositories in a spreadsheet. First decisions were made on what information is needed to categorise e-journals and open access repositories. The collection is a major step towards a landscape analysis, which

will help us to determine whether there exists a specific desideratum for a new e-journal or open access repository that PARTHENOS might be able to fulfil. This also requires the development of a common understanding of the scope of scientific communication as the PARTHENOS target areas are very heterogeneous. This is an inherently dynamic and open-ended process as the modalities of scientific communication are in a state of flux.

Furthermore, we have setup a Zotero library, and have started to populate it with references to literature regarding scientific communication in the arts and humanities and particularly to enhanced publications.⁴

In summary, the outcomes of our activities in the first year are:

- a collection of literature on enhanced publication;
- a structured approach to collect necessary information on existing e-journals and open access repositories including first examples;
- first considerations on evaluation criteria to decide where the gaps are and if there is a need to implement a new e-journal and/or repositories;
- preliminary reflections on alternative modes of scientific communication.

⁴https://www.zotero.org/groups/parthenos_wp2/items/collectionKey/M9EKQQW7

5. Summary evaluation of activities during first year

Table 5 offers a summary evaluation of our activities reported in detail above against the performance targets set in the Initial Communication Plan.

Indicator	Target (by month 12)	Actual (by month 12)
Avg. number of website visitors per month	200	377
Total number of website visitors	1,000	4,526
Number of EU/EEA countries reached through website	25	31 (all countries)
Total number of referrals	200	1241
Number of contacts in the mailing list	150	162
Number of twitter followers	100	208
Avg. monthly number of tweet impressions	800	5,702
Number of joint events	0-1	0
Number of attendees at joint events	0-50	0
Number of press releases	3	8
Number of leaflets/other publicity materials distributed	300	4,030 (to partners)
Number of presentations/posters at conferences, workshops, etc.	6	Ca. 12
Number of attendees reached at conferences	150	500 (estimated)
Number of scientific papers	0	0
Articles in professional journals and online newsletters	3	13

Table 5: Evaluation against targets

As can be seen we have reached, and in many cases significantly exceeded, all our performance targets.

6. Planning of activities for second year

6.1. Website

The main aim for the project's second year is to ensure that that we keep on increasing visitor numbers and the user retention rate to the PARTHENOS website.

In terms of content, given that more and more activities and tasks are expected to produce their first results over the coming twelve months, we expect an increase in the overall number of news items released, mainly in the project-related news category (see above section 4.1.1 for a description of the categorisation).

Together with DARIAH-EU and EHRI, we are also planning the release of a flagship, long-form feature article which will describe the core concepts and benefits of EU Research Infrastructure initiatives later in 2016. The feature, which is currently under development, is intended to be media-enriched and designed to engage not only professionals and academics interested in the topic, but also the general public and policy-makers. Given its interactive form, the feature will be hosted on a different platform than parthenos-project.eu. This will ensure a high level of freedom in terms of design and technical possibilities. The feature will nevertheless be referenced from parthenos-project.eu.

6.2. Social media

Regarding our social media strategy for the second year, we will first of all focus on sustaining and expanding what we have, especially the Twitter account. Twitter still is one of the most effective social media channels when it comes to reaching an academic target group. It also creates a lot of referrals to the project website. We will continue our efforts to get more followers and to increase the impressions of our tweets.

As the project develops and produces more results, we will increase our use of two other existing social media channels: YouTube and SlideShare. Both have proven their value in disseminating results in other, similar projects.

In the second year, we will also investigate the use of other social media for PARTHENOS' dissemination purposes, mainly Facebook, LinkedIn and Instagram.

Although Facebook may not appear to be an obvious candidate for communicating PARTHENOS to its target groups, it still delivers a certain amount of referrals to our website (see figure 10) even though PARTHENOS itself has hitherto not been active on Facebook. It may therefore be worthwhile to start a PARTHENOS Facebook page.

6.3. Mailing list

At the end of the first year 162 individuals had been subscribed to our mailing list. 104 people were bulk subscribed at the start of the project, whereas 58 individuals self-registered via the PARTHENOS' website.

For the second year, we aim at gradually increasing our subscriber base by taking a more active approach to getting people subscribed. We will promote subscriptions via our social media channels and website, and we will additionally seek the help of our partners.

Apart for sending out the newsletter, we also intend to increasingly use the mailing list for other dissemination purposes such as invitations to workshops, etc.

6.4. Newsletters

The PARTHENOS newsletter is a good vehicle to keep our stakeholders updated about the project's progress, increase their involvement, and to increase traffic to the PARTHENOS website.

We intend to publish at least four newsletters during the second year. As we expect the amount of project-internal news to grow, we do not foresee any difficulties in sourcing sufficient news items to reach this target. Rather than following a set publication schedule, we will continue to take a flexible approach, and let the availability of pertinent news determine the timing and exact frequency of Newsletter issues.

6.5. Press relations

As stated in section 4.5, we propose to follow a “smart approach” regarding the issuing of press releases. This means that instead of fixing a number of press releases per year, we will rather focus on issuing releases once appropriate content is available

Currently we envisage the next round of press releases to take place around the launch of the feature news on Research Infrastructures in the autumn of 2016 (see section 6.1 for details).

6.6. Publicity materials

The first goal for the second project year is to maintain and manage the existing publicity materials (flyer, general PowerPoint presentation and poster), and to create updated versions as the project progresses.

We will, furthermore, provide assistance to other work packages that want to create publicity materials to promote their outputs and findings.

Finally, given that we expect that PARTHENOS will start to (co-)organise events over the coming year, we will investigate whether there is a need for additionally publicity material that is specifically geared towards these events, for instance PARTHENOS’ templates for programmes, badges, folders or special flyers. At a later stage, and if there is demand, we could also think of creating PARTHENOS’ merchandise such as pens, bags, mugs, etc.

6.7. Publications

We expect that most substantive, peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to PARTHENOS will be published in the second half of the project, and we do not yet envisage much activity in this regard during the second year. However, we intend to keep on publishing smaller articles and news items that focus on the project’s goals, background and first, preliminary results.

6.8. Events

6.8.1. External events

The Basecamp calendars mentioned in section 4.8.1 above will continue to be maintained and updated, and period reminders will be sent to partners to encourage them to disseminate information about PARTHENOS at events they are attending. All partners will be notified of calls for papers considered to be relevant to PARTHENOS, and invited to submit posters, papers and similar. Many partners are already active within their own domains with regards to participation at workshops and conferences, e.g. LREC for linguistic studies, CAA and EAA for archaeology.

6.8.2. Joint events

As explained in section above, our attempts to co-organise a first joint event at DH2016 was unsuccessful. In view of this setback, the events calendar was inspected for other suitable opportunities but nothing appeared to be as good a fit – for example, iPRES is narrowly focused on preservation and EuroMed (in Cyprus, an awkward destination for travelling to and from) was judged to have too broad a topic matter to be suitable for our purposes. After consultation with all WP leaders and other RIs in PARTHENOS, it was decided to hold our first joint event in the second year.

We are currently planning to organise a first PARTHENOS joint event during the ARIADNE Final Conference which will take place 15-16 December 2016 in Florence, Italy. The ARIADNE Final Conference is very promising in terms of timing and location, and, thanks to the involvement of PIN in both ARIADNE and PARTHENOS, should be relatively straight-forward in regard to organisation. A short document with initial ideas about format and theme of a PARTHENOS workshop has been written, and feedback from all WP Leaders has been sought. We expect to be able to finalise the programme for this workshop in Autumn 2016.

Furthermore, we will be closely inspecting the events calendar for opportunities for an additional joint event during 2017. The annual Digital Humanities (DH) conference will not be hosted in Europe for another two years, and will therefore be targeted in the final year. In the meantime, other suitable events will be identified.

Finally, DARIAH is set to be included as a formal partner in PARTHENOS from Year 2. DARIAH's agreed tasks include two joint DARIAH-PARTHENOS Workshops to be held in Years 3 and 4 of the project.

6.9. Scientific communication

In the second year we will continue, and bring to a conclusion, our activities of the first year. In particular, we will enlarge the existing collection of relevant e-journals and open access repositories with the help of the PARTHENOS partners to build a broader basis to decide if a new journal and/or open access repository is needed.

Depending on the results of this landscape study, we will then proceed to draft a plan for implementation. This would include a list of specifications of the new e-journal and/or open access repository, and a first outline on how to implement these step by step in the second half of the project.

In the context of the enormous growth of social media and other, related communication methods, scientific communication is currently undergoing a process of change. In addition to establishing the requirements for an e-journal/OA repository, we will also consider whether PARTHENOS should support alternative ways of scientific communication. We will start by collecting information on existing relevant initiatives such as the general approaches provided by OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>), including the services of ZENODO (<http://zenodo.org/>), or relevant activities of associated RIs such as DARIAH, EHRI, etc. We will collect information on how our specific PARTHENOS target groups undertake their scientific communication besides articles in journals or in repositories such as scholarly social networks (for instance ResearchGate, <https://www.researchgate.net/>, or www.academia.edu), or scientific blogs.

Following these two trajectories, we intend to be back on schedule for this task at the end of the second year. In particular, by the end of year two, we aim to have finished our requirements gathering, and have a firm strategy on how we will support scientific communication in place.

7. Evaluation criteria for year 2

Indicator	Target (by month 24)
Total number of website visitors	4,500
Number of EU/EEA countries reached through website	31
Total number of referrals	1,000
Number of contacts in the mailing list	200
Number of twitter followers	400
Avg. monthly number of tweet impressions	8,000
Number of joint events	1-2
Avg. number of attendees at joint events	30
Number of leaflets/other publicity materials distributed (to partners)	500
Number of presentations/posters at conferences, workshops, etc.	6-8
Number of attendees reached at conferences	200
Number of scientific papers	0-1
Articles in professional journals and online newsletters	5

Table 6: Evaluation criteria Year 2